

Purification of SLC25A37 from Expi293F™ Cells

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Protocol description

This protocol is used to purify the SLC transporter expressed in Expi293F™ Cells using detergent solubilization followed by a series of different chromatographic methods. Depending on the nature of the expression construct and experimental requirements, the GFP tag can be removed using a proteolytic reaction.

Materials

Biological materials:	
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ HEPES (Apollo Scientific, catalog number BI8181)▪ NaCl (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number S9888)▪ n-Dodecyl-b-D-maltopyranoside (DDM) (Anatrace, catalog number D310)▪ Cholesteryl Hemisuccinate Tris Salt (Anatrace, catalog number CH210)▪ cOmplete™, EDTA-free Protease Inhibitor Cocktail (Roche, catalog number 11873580001)▪ Magnesium Chloride Hexahydrate (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number M2670)▪ Adenosine 5-triphosphate disodium salt hydrate, Sigma Aldrich catalog number A2383)▪ Potassium Chloride (KCl) (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number P3911)▪ D(+)-Biotin (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number 851209)▪ 3C protease (Glutathione S-transferase tagged) (3C-GST) produced in-house
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ WHEATON® Dounce Tissue Grinder, 40 mL (DWK Life Sciences, catalog number 357546)▪ Gravity flow columns▪ 50 or 100 kDa cut-off centrifugal concentrators▪ 96 well block (2 mL)

Reagents setup

- **Stock Solution:** 100 mM ATP –NaOH pH 7.4
- **Stock Solution:** 5% (w/v) DDM/CHS in the ratio of 10:1, prepared in Base buffer. Rotate at 4 °C overnight to allow complete solubilisation and store at -20 °C.
- **Stock Solution:** 250 mM D-biotin in Base buffer. Adjust the pH with NaOH to 7.4 and store at -20 °C.
- Base buffer (150 mM NaCl, 25 mM HEPES pH 7.4)
- Wash buffer 1 (25 mM HEPES pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM ATP-NaOH, 5 mM MgCl₂, 50 mM KCl, 0.03% DDM/CHS)
- Wash Buffer 2 (25 mM HEPES pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 50 mM KCl, 0.03% DDM/CHS)
- Strep elution buffer (25 mM HEPES pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 100 mM Biotin, 0.03% DDM/CHS)
- SEC buffer (20 mM HEPES-NaOH pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 0.02% DDM/CHS), filtered through 0.22 µM membrane

Procedure

▪ Part A of protocol / day 1

1. Thaw the frozen cell pellet in a water bath set to room temperature.
3. Add 100 µM Biotin and 3 tablets of Protease Inhibitor Cocktail tablet to 150 mL of base buffer containing 1% DDM/CHS. Allow the tablets to dissolve.

4. Suspend thawed pellets with solubilization buffer and pour into a Dounce homogeniser. Homogenise the solution by pulling and pushing the plunger up and down approximately 20 times. Keep on ice.
4. Rotate the container slowly for 1 hour at 4 °C.
5. Centrifuge the solution at 50,000 x g for 30 minutes at 4 °C.
6. Equilibrate 10-15 mL bed volume of anti-GFP resin with the Wash buffer 1. Add equilibrated anti-GFP resin to the supernatant from step 5, put on a rotator and rotate for 1 hour at 4 °C.
7. Pour the solution into an empty gravity flow column, allow the solution to flow through.
8. Wash the resin with 10 times the bed volume of Wash buffer 1.
9. Wash the resin with 200 mL of Wash buffer 2.
10. Add 2 mg of 3C-GST to the resin on-column and incubate overnight at 4 °C.

▪ **Part B of protocol / day 2**

11. Add 30-40 ml of Wash buffer 2 and collect the flow through. The flow through contains the SLC protein and the 3C protease.
12. Perform a reverse chromatography using Glutathione resin column. The SLC protein should be in the first flow through. Collect the flow through solution in a 100 kDa cut-off centrifugal filter.
13. Measure protein concentration using nanodrop.
14. Concentrate the solution by centrifuging at 3,000 xg at 4 °C, stop and gently agitate every 5 minutes.
15. Equilibrate a Superose 6 Increase 10/300 GL column using SEC buffer.
16. Concentrate the sample down to the desired injection volume and inject the sample into the sample loop.
17. Run a SEC elution.
18. Pool peak fractions in a fresh 100 kDa cut-off centrifugal concentrator and concentrate to the required volume/concentration at 3,000 xg at 4 °C.

Additional notes

1. The amount of solubilisation buffer depends on the cell pellet volume. We recommend using 30-40 mL solubilisation buffer per litre cell culture. The above protocol has been adapted for cell pellet from 4 L culture.

Data availability

References

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.